

**PSYCHOLINGUISTIC BASIS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE
TEACHING METHODOLOGY IN PRIMARY GRADES**

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ANNOTATION: In this article, it is mainly given about the psycholinguistic basis of the methodology in teaching English to young children.

KEY WORDS: linguophysiology, neurolinguistics, dynamic stereotype, contrastive analysis, speech development phylogeny, potential vocabulary.

Human speech is scientifically studied in the physiology of speech (linguophysiology), the occurrence and perception of speech in psycholinguistics.

Speech is a complex mental process that controls the activity of a person's brain, and its sound and literal aspects are expressed in external (material), speech, hearing, sight, and hand gestures. Both constitute a dynamic speech stereotype. It is known from the researches of I.P. Pavlov that a dynamic stereotype is a system of coordinated and stabilized signs consisting of conditional and unconditional reflexes. The reason why this system is called dynamic, that is, a system in motion, is that it can be destroyed and restored again. Each stereotype serves to express a certain meaning and creates responses to stimuli of different levels. In turn, the operation of stereotypes creates a speech mechanism as a language tool.

Mother tongue is important in learning English. That is, any foreign language is learned through the prism of the mother tongue. Skills and competencies in a foreign language are acquired through the skills and competencies acquired in the mother tongue. The transfer of skills is an urgent problem in teaching English to teenagers, and especially to adults.

It is known from the research that the language experiences of elementary school students are not developed to the level of distinguishing the differences between the mother tongue and English. Also, the brains of young language learners are physiologically not fully adapted to the grammatical laws that regulate word formation and sentence structure in their native language.

Adults analyze cross-linguistic differences because they have some knowledge of their mother tongue and English. This leads to hesitancy and inhibition in the process of speech activity. According to experts in the field, the success of young students in learning English lies in the fact that they pay attention to the concept rather than the sentence, the content rather than the grammatical device, that is, the form, and do not fall into hesitation and inhibitions during the interaction.

F.I. Fradkina dealt with the problem of the formation of early active speech in children. In his experience, during natural communication, a child learned a word in one day, but in artificial conditions, he was able to show the image of the object

expressed by that word for 10-11 days. A new word in the mother tongue is acquired when a strong connection is established between the object or event it represents and its verbal alternative. For this purpose, the child learns to perform the actions that are intended to be performed with the objects that surround him, that is, the quality of the object that comes from its own characteristics, such as color, shape, and taste. and should understand the task correctly.

In the process of learning English, the student will have a certain level of understanding of the objects and their functions. Effectiveness of learning English is ensured in a situation where a strong connection is established with the English equivalent of the word in the student's mind. According to I.A.Zimnyaya, this very situation prevents the new word from being consolidated in the student's memory, and on the other hand, it creates the need to make maximum use of the student's language experience during the learning process.

The difference between the Uzbek and English languages is shown as the reason for the mistakes made by the students. The main difference between Uzbek and English is that they belong to different language families. While English is an analytic language, Uzbek language belongs to the category of both inflectional and agglutinative languages. In English, the sentence structure is subject to a strict order, and in most cases the sequence of possessive - participle - secondary clauses is followed. This serves to optimize the process of learning English. The order of words in the English sentence structure clearly shows who is doing the action and what it is aimed at. Various methods were used in the practice of teaching sentence formation in English at the junior school age. For example, F.Guin's (Series Method) imitation exercises based on series of action sequences and J.Asher's (Total Physical Response) methods are widely popular.

The results of the researchers' experimental work show that the order of learning morphemes in English by elementary school students does not depend on the extent to which their native language differs from English.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED:

1. Mamajonova N. "BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA INGLIZ TILI O'QITISH METODIKASINING PSIXOLINGVISTIK ASOSLARI".
2. <https://www.intereuroconf.com/index.php/DESH/article/download/1321/1059>
3. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334794715_The_Role_of_Psycholinguistics_in_Language_Learning_and_Teaching
4. <https://journal.um-surabaya.ac.id/index.php/Tell/article/view/2077>
5. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372334253_Psychology_of_language_learning